

Sustainable Supplier Selection in the context of Circular Economy

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable supplier selection boosts the potential for a circular economy (CE): conserving resources, minimizing waste, and mitigating possibly harmful environmental impact. This paper proposes a holistic framework for sustainable supplier evaluation and selection, developed based on the economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Traditional approaches to supplier selection concentrate more on economic and qualitative characteristics, while the sustainable supplier selection highlights on social, economic and environmental parameters. The utilization of the entropy-TOPSIS method is a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) approach that lays an objective ground for evaluating and ranking suppliers according to their contributions toward circularity and sustainability. In this research, entropy method has been used to calculate the weights of each of the parameters based on available data which has an impact on the normalized decision matrix of Technique for order preference similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS) model. A case study has been presented and result shows the sustainable supplier who takes care of sustainable supply chain management strategy based on CE principles: better resource utilization, compliance with environmental regulations, and superior competitive advantage. By merging circular economy principles with the entropy-TOPSIS method, manufacturers could establish more resilient and environmentally-friendly supply chains that reduce waste, environmental impacts, and long-term resource sustainability.

KEYWORDS: *Circular Economy (CE), Circular Supplier Selection, Entropy, TOPSIS, MCDM, Sustainable Manufacturing.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable supplier selection is an important part of the circular economy, circular economy practice, and balancing social, environmental, and economic issues. The future-facing economy will build products that minimize the waste generated; maximize efficiency in resourcing and sustainability adoption at life-span level for the product. Socially, the sustainable supplier selection process confirms that suppliers are engaged in fair labor practices, pay equitable wages, and encourage the development of local communities. Environmentally, this process selects suppliers that aim to minimize carbon emissions, utilize renewable energy, and apply sustainable practices within their industrial operations. Economically, sustainable supplier selection gives a long-term view on financial viability by considering cost-effective and quality materials along with creating innovations directed towards profits without compromising sustainability. By bringing these three pillars—the social environment and economic one can achieve strong sustainable supply chains, that protect circular economy principles while providing sustainability and double value to the organization and society.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dolci et al. (2024) [1] demonstrated that CE is in highlight after these modern days with limited resources available. With the increasing population every passing day, the overall consumption of resources is increasing along with it. At the same time, that which sustains would have to be thought out, for the future saving of resources. waste would be required to generate less, and to achieve that will maximize the utilization of waste. "Reducing waste, maximizing the use of resources, and developing closed-loop systems—where materials and products are recycled, refurbished, or reused rather than thrown away" is the process of choosing suppliers who share the principles of a circular economy, minimizing the impact on the environment. Resource

efficiency, waste minimization, material recycling and reuse, and sustainable practices all benefit from CSS.

Numerous literature reviews have already been done for this research; a few of them are mentioned below:

Dolci et al. (2024) [1] identified key elements of a circular and sustainable production system and demonstrates how Industry 4.0 technologies can be implemented to manufacturing industry. They have used Systematic literature review (SLR) method. **Nikolakis et al.** (2024) [2] developed a methodology that promotes decision-making at a manufacturing process enhancing more sustainable strategy. They have used Life cycle assessment (LCA), Life cycle cost (LCC) analysis & Eco-efficiency analysis methods. **Dwivedi et al.** (2023) [3] analyzed the contribution of technological innovation towards sustainability in manufacturing organizations with a circular economy (CE). They have used Grey VIKOR method & sensitivity analysis methods. **Schögl et al.** (2023) [4] addressed this research gap through descriptive, hierarchical cluster and non-parametric analyses of the use of DTs for circular economy and sustainability management. They have used Hierarchical cluster & non-parametric analysis (Kruskal-Wallis tests and Spearman rank correlations) methods. **Khan et al.** (2025) [5] analyzed the transition from linear economy to circular economy practices for manufacturing SMEs operating in developing countries. They have used Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), Descriptive statistics & Hypotheses testing methods. **Ijassi et al.** (2024) [6] proposed a framework that represents a set of pedagogical specifications for both hard and soft skills required to design sustainable and circular proposals for urban factories. They have used Life cycle assessment (LCA), Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities & threats (SWOT) analysis methods. **Rashid et al.** (2025) [7] developed a framework to identify and analyze the industry's transition to a circular economy, reduce environmental impact, and promote sustainable growth. They have used Fuzzy theory & DEMATEL methods. **Faheem et al.** (2024) [8] demonstrate the framework Meta analysis (PRISMA) and systemic reviews through circular economy, life cycle assessment, environmental aspects and recycled materials. They have used Meta analysis (PRISMA) & Systematic literature review (SLR) methods. **Haq et al.** (2023) [9] applied the circular economy principle of 'reusing' to manage the pre-consumer waste sustainability generated in the cutting section of the textile industry. They have used Circular Economy Principles method.

Few studies on circular supplier selection have been conducted in developing nations; nearly all of the study to far has been conducted in wealthy nations. The tools employed lack implicit practical significance, and the frameworks created by earlier studies are not very operationalized. Small and medium-sized businesses have limited access to specialized technology and software needed to gather the required data. The researchers only dealt with a few noteworthy parameters, and the data set employed in the earlier studies was small. No prior work has been done on the three most crucial CE parameters: social, environmental, and economic.

The rigorous literature review identifies key issues related to sustainable supplier selection, the recognition of a benchmarked industry, and the sustainable strategies to be followed by other supplier organizations. To address these aspects, this study proposes a combined Entropy-TOPSIS approach, which has not been previously exercised by any researcher.

The study design is explained in the part that follows. Section 4 has already covered the case study. Section 5 has focused on discussions. Whereas Section 6 has addressed conclusion with limitations and future scope.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

The proposed model has been described in Fig.1

Figure 1. Proposed framework of adopted methodology.

After an extensive literature review, the questionnaire was designed for sustainable supplier selection based on sustainable parameters in the context of the circular economy. The questionnaire consists of the identified parameters and their corresponding values for the case organizations. The criteria considered in this study are explained in Table 1. Once industrial data is collected from the organizations, the decision matrix is formed. The preference value of each parameter is calculated using the entropy methodology. The weight of each parameter is multiplied by the decision matrix.

Table 1. Sustainable Parameters.

Notation	Criteria	Unit	Type	Nature
C1	Total raw material consumption	(Tons)	Environmental	Minimizing
C2	Reduction in total emission	(%)	Environmental	Maximizing
C3	Invest in CSR	(Crore/Year)	Social	Maximizing
C4	Total out reach of health and hygiene program	NA	Social	Maximizing
C5	Savings in total energy cost	(Crore/Year)	Economical	Maximizing
C6	Returns from sale of recycled waste products	(Crore/Year)	Economical	Maximizing

The detailed steps are as follows:

Step-1: The decision matrix is formed as follows: Eq. (1)

$$X_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & X_{12} & \dots & X_{1n} \\ X_{21} & X_{22} & \dots & X_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ X_{m1} & X_{m2} & \dots & X_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad X_{ii} = 1, X_{ij} = \frac{1}{X_{ji}}, X_{ji} \neq 0 \quad (1)$$

Where X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n is denoted as criteria.

Step-2: The normalized decision matrix X_{ij}^* is calculated using following Eq. (2). The main objective of the normalization process is to obtain dimensionless values of different criteria to make comparison between them.

$$n_{ij}^* = \frac{X_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m X_{ij}^2}} \quad (2)$$

The Entropy value of y_j j^{th} criteria can be obtained as:

$$y_j = -k \sum_{i=1}^m n_{ij}^* \ln(n_{ij}^*) \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

Where $k = \frac{1}{\ln(m)}$ m denotes the number of alternatives used in the study and it is between

$0 \leq y_j \leq 1$. The degrees of divergence (d_j) of the average information contained by each criterion can be obtained from Eq. (4):

$$d_j = |1 - y_j| \quad (4)$$

Thus, the entropy weight of the j^{th} criteria can be defined as:

$$w_j = \frac{d_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n d_j}$$

Step-3: The normalized decision matrix multiplies with associated weights and its formed $V_{ij} = n_{ij} W_{ij} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n; i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ (2)

Step-4: The positive and negative ideal solutions are determined using Eq. In below (3) and (4) respectively:

$$\{V_1^+, V_2^+, \dots, V_n^+\} = \{MaxV_{ij} | j \in K, (MinV_{ij} | j \in K') | i = 1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad (3)$$

$$\{V_1^-, V_2^-, \dots, V_n^-\} = \{MinV_{ij} | j \in K, (MaxV_{ij} | j \in K') | i = 1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad (4)$$

Where K is the index set of benefit criteria and K' is the index of cost criteria.

Step-5: The distance from the positive ideal and negative solutions computed by below equations (5) and (6) respectively:

$$S_i^+ = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n (V_{ij} - V_j^+)^2 \right\}^{0.5} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (5)$$

$$S_i^- = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n (V_{ij} - V_j^-)^2 \right\}^{0.5} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (6)$$

Step-6: Relative closeness is computed using equation (7):

$$P_i = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^+ + S_i^-} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad 0 \leq C_i \leq 1 \quad (7)$$

Result of equation (7) Contain higher value is best rank and smallest value got worst rank that means ranking is in decreasing order.

4. CASE STUDY

The following technique has been created in order to achieve the goals of the study. First, three small-scale, India-based businesses that adhere to the circular economy—Company-A, Company-B, and Company-C—are chosen. To gather the necessary data for questionnaire design, the specialists at the following companies have been visited in person and consulted by email. This is done in order to identify which of the three businesses listed above best meets all of the requirements of the circular economy.

After the following steps the final data matrix is designed.

Table 2. industrial data

Notation	Nature	COMPANY A	COMPANY B	COMPANY C
C1	Minimizing	504918	1064598	2400000
C2	Maximizing	29	17	35
C3	Maximizing	25.91	22.9	291
C4	Maximizing	835433	998563	547886
C5	Maximizing	127.5	87.69	95.67
C6	Maximizing	1023	2762	997

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This study uses an integrated Multi Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) technology to identify the best circular supplier. Weights are evaluated using the entropy approach, and TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) methodology is used for ranking. The companies' yearly sustainability reports, expert consultations, and the creation of questionnaires are the methods used to gather primary or secondary data.

The decision matrix is created by further analyzing the expert data that was gathered. The choice matrix can be seen below:

Step-1: The decision matrix is developed as stated in Eq. (1):

Table 3. Decision Matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
COMPANY A	504918	29	25.91	835433	127.5	1023
COMPANY B	1064598	17	22.9	998563	87.69	2762
COMPANY C	2400000	35	291	547886	95.67	997

Step-2: The normalized decision matrix is developed from Eq. (2), Eq. (3) & Eq. (4):

Table 4. Normalized Decision Matrix.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
W_j	0.184	0.042	0.603	0.029	0.014	0.128
COMPANY A	0.127	0.358	0.076	0.351	0.410	0.214
COMPANY B	0.268	0.210	0.067	0.419	0.282	0.578
COMPANY C	0.605	0.432	0.856	0.230	0.308	0.208

Step 3: The weighted normalized decision matrix is formulated from Eq. (2) & Eq. (4):

Table 5. Weighted Normalized Matrix.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
COMPANY A	0.034	0.024	0.053	0.017	0.009	0.042
COMPANY B	0.073	0.014	0.047	0.020	0.006	0.113
COMPANY C	0.165	0.030	0.599	0.011	0.011	0.007

Step 4: The positive and negative ideal solution is constructed from Eq. (3) & Eq. (4) respectively:

$$v^+ = \{0.034\}, \{0.030\}, \{0.599\}, \{0.020\}, \{0.009\}, \{0.113\}$$

$$v^- = \{0.165\}, \{0.014\}, \{0.047\}, \{0.011\}, \{0.006\}, \{0.041\}$$

Step 5: The distance from positive ideal to negative ideal solution is developed from Eq. (5) & Eq. (6) respectively:

$$S_i^+ = \{0.550\}, \{0.553\}, \{0.150\}$$

$$S_i^- = \{0.131\}, \{0.117\}, \{0.552\}$$

Step 6: Finally, the relative closeness is determined from Eq. (7):

$$P_i = \{0.192\}, \{0.175\}, \{0.787\}$$

5. DISCUSSIONS

The numerical result shows that $C3 > C1 > C6$.

It means that C3 (Investment in CSR) is the main motto of the benchmark supplier. Then C1 (Total Raw Material Consumption) is the next most important criteria of the supplier. Lastly, C6 (Returns from the sale of recycled waste products) is the third most valuable criteria for the leading supplier. In this research Entropy methodology have been used to accurately determine the preference weights. It is the only method in which preference weight is calculated using the decision matrix. TOPSIS methodology is used because it is the only tool of MCDM that is based on distance-based optimization.

6. CONCLUSIONS

As determined from this research, the final outcome of the ranking of the companies is given by:

Company C > Company A > Company B

Hence from this result it can be concluded that Company C secured the top rank therefore it is called as benchmark organization. Because it has implemented or adopted various circular economy practices efficiently into its supply chain. According to this research as it is the benchmark industry therefore it can lead other organization in implementing circular economy or show a path for future reference. Other companies must implement their strategy for enhancing more sustainable circular economy practices.

Here, in this research only three companies are taken into account. So, in future this sample size may be increased by some other researchers for further study. The researchers can apply the same framework developed in this research which will give more robust and validated result.

In this paper the data for a developing country is considered. This research can be further conducted for more than one country or a developed country and compare the same.

For the calculation purpose only six criteria are taken. For further research scope the number of criterions may be increased to get more enhanced result.

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